

Advancements in Composite Materials: Development and Experimental Analysis of Banana and Bamboo Fiber Reinforced Polyester Composites

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Abstract:

The development of bamboo and banana-reinforced polyester composite was the subject of the investigation. For a hybrid polymer composite, two cellulosic fibers are used as reinforcement because of their affordability, availability, and environmentally beneficial waste disposal. Furthermore, the highly fibrous and hydrophilic fibers are collected locally, which enables them to create a strong bond with the polyester polymeric matrix in the form of particle fibers. Thus, the purpose of this study is to examine the application of banana and bamboo fiber in composite construction. Composites were made by hand lay-up method using a waste natural resource

mixture of banana and bamboo fiber for reinforcement. Samples that have been separated and developed are evaluated for their thermal and mechanical characteristics. All processes are showed in the graphical abstract in Figure 1. Using the hybrid composite to its advantage, three samples were created and examined. According to the data, the composite with the excess bamboo fiber exhibits greater performance than the other two samples. In conclusion, when combined with bamboo fiber in small amounts, banana fiber's adequate elasticity can improve the qualities. The sample exhibits favorable properties in the bend, impact, and thermal conductivity tests.

Keywords: Composite, Polyester Resin, Sustainability, Bamboo Fiber, Banana Fiber.

Introduction

Composites are robust materials with notable qualities for cutting edge use. They amalgamate and furnish their most advantageous characteristics to enhance the result or ultimate product (Bishnoi, Singh, & Mangal, 2023). Usually, composites are created with a specific purpose in mind, like increased durability, strength, or efficiency. By the amalgamation of

two or more materials with different physical and chemical properties produce composite (Raju, & Shanmugaraja, 2020). Through this advancement, the final materials have desirable properties that could bring new scope in the field of advanced application. According to the global market analysis, fiber reinforced polymer composite has reached around \$2.1 billion market value in 2010. This market has been expanding due to the growing demand and new

scopes for application (Khalid, et al., 2021). Beside numerous engineering disciplines, automotive sectors, structural components, packaging sectors and construction applications gained a lot of interest in the application of polymer composite (An, et al., 2023). Although fibers from a variety of materials can be utilized as reinforcement. Among them, basalt, glass, and carbon are the most popular choices. Other significant reinforcing fibers are natural fibers like cotton, hemp, flax, bamboo, banana, luffa, palmyra and so on as well as some synthetic fibers are also popular like polyester, aramid fibers (brand name Kevlar) etc (Di Bella, Fiore, & Valenza, 2012). Though synthetic fiber reinforcement provides better physical,

mechanical and thermal properties of the composite in comparison with the natural fiber, sustainability and environmental wellness can only be achieved by using natural fiber reinforcement (An, et al., 2023). These reinforcements are added to the matrix material to boost the mechanical and thermal characteristics for the further application (Ramakrishna, et al., 2021). There are several factors behind the popularity of the fiber reinforced polymer composite (NFPC) such as low specific weight, relatively high strength, low production cost, corrosion resistance, fatigue resistance, biodegradability, adaptability of functional finishes of the composite materials (Raju, & Shanmugaraja, 2020).

Figure 1. Graphical Abstract

Source: Own Work.

Dependency on natural fibers as reinforcement can open a door for sustainability and effective uses of natural resources (Abdollahiparsa, et al., 2023). In this research, bamboo and banana fibers have been used as reinforcement materials in this Natural Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composite (NFPC). This is aiming to form

affordable, light-weight and green composite for achieving great qualities for advanced application (Abdollahiparsa, et al., 2023). Bamboo fibers have many great qualities including high tensile strength, high strength to weight ratio, lower cost than other synthetic fibers, ease of availability and eco-friendliness.

The Fast growing and renew-ability of bamboo fiber make it suitable for advanced research and making user friendly products (Liu, et al., 2012). The strength of bamboo has been compared with traditional wood. For this reason, researchers found the strength of bamboo is ten times stronger than traditional wood. The bamboo based products which are available in the markets are made from 70% recycled bamboo and 30% high density polyethylene (HDPE). Since, bamboo based composite gained more attention in the composite world for the light-weight nature and water repellent properties (Hasan, et al., 2023). Another important fiber for composite manufacturing is banana fiber. This fiber can be obtained with no expense, as this fiber has been grown in the rural area for banana cultivation (Rao, et al., 2021). Though the fiber extraction can be important to maintain the overall fiber quality, an excellent fiber extruder can mitigate fiber damage and make an effective way to maintain fiber strength, luster and effectiveness. Banana fiber's multiple celled linear cellulosic structure, thick wall and very few cross marks make it a sound reinforcement with polyester resin (Jeyaraj, et al., 2024). This fiber is compared with traditional glass fiber based on its specific strength qualities (Nagaraja, et al., 2020). Beside the other factors, another most important factor is the exceptional length of banana fiber that significantly improves the composite characteristics (Sourisolut, et al., 2024). In comparison to the composite qualities, fiber is very important. An 8–12% increase in fiber length increases the composite's tensile and flexural strengths. As a result, banana fiber has superior mechanical and thermal qualities (Jeyaraj, et al., 2024).

Natural fiber composites show better thermo-mechanical and electrical properties, if the interfacial bonds between the matrix and fibers are strong enough. The traditional matrix resins used for fiber-reinforced plastics include epoxy, vinyl esters, polyester, and phenol resins (Raju, & Shanmugaraja, 2021). Moreover, highly expensive high-performance resins, such as polyimide, cyanate ester, and BMI resins, are employed for high-end applications (Narayanan, & Elayaperumal, 2010). For making a fiber

reinforced polymer composite material, polyester resin is an essential substance that creates an important role in the composite manufacturing. The shape of the polymer composite depends on the low viscosity unsaturated polyester resin and creates an impact on making thermosetting polymer composite (Yamini, et al., 2023). While previous research provides in-sights into numerous combinations of fibers for making the fiber reinforced polymer composite, banana and bamboo fibers combinations are quite meager (Balamurugan, et al., 2023). As of now, there is less data available on natural fibers reinforcement with banana and bamboo fiber. In particular, no meaningful information is available for these studies regarding the type of resin that should be utilized with banana and bamboo fibers and how the combination of these fibers improves the qualities of the composite. This work is innovative because it pays particular attention to figuring out the ideal mechanical and thermal properties of NFPC made of bamboo and banana fiber.

Materials and Methods

Materials

There are several ways of extracting bamboo fibers such as chemical extraction, mechanical and chemical combined extraction. Chemical extraction involves degumming, alkali and acid retting and chemical retting (Deshpande, Rao, & Lakshmana Rao, 2000). On the other hand, mechanical and chemically combined extraction involves steam explosion technique, retting, crushing, grinding, rolling etc (Zakikhani, et al., 2014). Due to lack of available methods and materials, this study was going through the manual hammering process. At first, Muli Bamboos (*Melocanna bambusoides*) were collected from the local market of Tangile, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Only internode of bamboo is collected for the composite making and bamboo nodes are avoided from the fiber extraction for achieving better quality (Deshpande, et al., 2000). Then the yellowish inner portion is splitted and spared as well as greenish outer skin is separated by the sharp edged tool. The fiber

extraction process is shown on the Figure 2. After collecting the fibrous portion of the bamboo fiber, manually hammer is used to beat it and make the fiber loose and separated for the further procedure. Once loose and separated

fibers are obtained, they are dried in the sunlight to dry the moisture on it. Banana fiber was collected from the local market of Modhupur, Tangile, Bangladesh.

Figure 2. Bamboo Fiber Extraction Process
Source: Own Work.

extraction. Biological retting process produce higher quality fiber but this process is laborious and time consuming and also requires lots of water. some additional organic compounds such as wax, lignin, pectin are found on the surface of the natural fibers which can act as barrier to destroy the proper inter- facial adhesion between filler and polymer matrix which can expressed by the following equation (Jeyaraj, et al., 2024).

$$\text{Volume fraction of Fiber } V_f = \frac{\frac{W_f}{\rho_f}}{\frac{W_f}{\rho_f} + \frac{W_m}{\rho_m}} \quad (1)$$

Where, W_m and W_f are the mass of the matrix and fiber and m and f are the density of matrix and fiber respectively (Zalameda, & Smith, 1994).

For that reason alkaline treatment is necessary for removing lignin from the natural fibers

materials. According to standard practice like the pulp and paper industry, rotten processes with alkaline treatment were used to remove lignin from the fibers (Rao, et al., 2021). After fragmenting lignin into smaller size, NaOH enables the lignin to dissolve in it. Then sheaths were pilled off in layer by layer and then splitted into two pseudostems (Jeyaraj, et al., 2024). After that the sheath is fed into the extraction machine and banana fibers are extracted by the friction of the rotary blade of the machine (Shinde, et al., 2018). After that, the fibers are removed, washed and dried in the shade for two to three hours. Naturally, untreated fibers are prone to absorb moisture that causes poor bonding between fibers and polymer matrix. Also significantly hampers the strength of the resulting composite. As natural fibers are hydrophilic, their moisture regain effect should be minimized. On the other hand, when a hydrophobic polyester matrix is combined with hydrophilic fibers which lead to poor adhesion, phase separation and limited

access load transfer resulting in composite foam (Pratikhya, Badanayak, & Bose, 2023). Bamboo and banana fibers are chopped 1-3 mm manually by scissors. Then the grinding process is done so that the fibers are mixed well with resin and provide equal density throughout the prepared liquid. Polyester resins are used as binder material for making NFPC. The resultant composite were tested as per ASTM: D638 standard for tensile test and ASTM: D790 for bending test.

Methods

Bamboo and banana fibers are trimmed into lengths of 1-3 mm, combined with polyester resin and hardener, and then left for 11–12 hours beneath a 10 kg dead weight. Samples A1, A2, and A3 are three samples that are organized. Each of the three specimens is made using the hand lay-up molding technique. First, the surface of the forming tool is coated with PVC and

aluminum foil to prevent the fiber-reinforced polymer from sticking. The polyester resin and fibers are combined with a hardener before being uniformly poured into the mold. The mixture is now spread out on a 16 × 16 cm baking tray.

The upper surface of the composite mix is then covered with another PVC sheet. Finally, 5 kg of primary weight was placed on the foil-molded resin tray to ensure even distribution. For 11–12 hours, load 10 kg of permanent weight after 10 minutes. For samples A1, A2, and A3, the combinations are 100:2.5:5:5 (polyester resin: Hardener: Bamboo fiber: Banana fiber), 100:2.5:7.5:2.5 (polyester resin: Hardener: Bamboo fiber: Banana fiber), and 100:2.5:2.5:7.5 (polyester resin: Hardener: Bamboo fiber: Banana fiber), respectively. The overall outlook of composite samples are visible in the figure 3. The volume, content, and orientation of samples A, B, and C are displayed in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Composition of Different Composite Samples

Sample	Orientation	Composition	Volume (%)
A ₁	Random	Polyester Resin, Hardener, Bamboo fiber (1-3 mm), Banana Fiber (1-3 mm)	100:2.5:5:5
A ₂	Random	Polyester Resin, Hardener, Bamboo Fiber (Size 1-3mm), Banana Fiber (Size 1- 3mm)	100:2.5:7.5:2.5
A ₃	Random	Polyester Resin, Hardener, Bamboo Fiber (Size 1-3mm), Banana Fiber (Size 1- 3mm)	100:2.5:7.5:7.5

Source: Own Work

Figure 3. Outlook of Different Composite Samples (A₁, A₂ and A₃)

Source: Own Work

After using these proportion according to the table, the composite samples A1, A2 and A3 were prepared. The visual representation of sample A1, A2 and A3 are given on the Figure 3.

This figure shows that all the three samples looks different due to the volume of individual fiber quantities during sample making process. Moreover, these samples are good for distinguishing different sample behavior according to the volume used in making the samples. There properties also changed according to the proportion added on the samples. Different mechanical tests were performed to know which sample showed good properties among them.

Results and Discussion

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

(SEM) is a test procedure where an electron beam scans a sample to create a magnified image that can be examined. The method also known as SEM microscopy and analysis is very helpful for failure analysis and microanalysis of solid inorganic materials (Hossain, 2012). High-resolution images and precise quantification of extremely small features and objects are produced by high-magnification electron microscopy. However, the samples were analyzed by SEM to know the morphological structure on composite and get the knowledge about the size, polydispersity, shape, purity, surface morphology and fiber distribution around the composite material (Tianyou, & Weizhou, 1998).

Figure 4. SEM Image of A₂ during Test

Source: Own Work

SEM is done for sample A2(100:2.5:7.5:2.5 (polyester resin: Hardener: Bamboo fiber: Banana fiber)). During the test the sample length was 10 cm and thickness was 2.5 cm. Sem is a microscope that uses a focused beam of electrons to scan a sample's surface to create a

high-resolution image. Here in sample A2, the SEM test which is stated in the Figure 4 was done to observe the void place of the fiber and resin distribution reaction. So, the A2 showed that the distributions of fiber and resin are not evenly done because of the hand lay-off process.

Tensile Strength Test

Tensile testing is a destructive test method used to determine a material's tensile strength and ductility. It gauges how much power is needed to shatter a composite (Zhu, Peled, & Mobasher, 2011). The ASTM D638 standard outlines how to test the tensile strength and determine the mechanical characteristics of plastics and other resin materials (Nossa, et al., 2019). It also describes the requirements for accuracy for the test frames and equipment used. In this test process, dumbbell-shaped specimens with gauge lengths of 25 mm or 50 mm are used. ASTM D638 requires a test drive precision that

meets ASTM E4 Course 1 requirements, which are accuracy within 1% of the demonstrated test drives. When it comes to composite materials this test gives a proper outline for the breaking strength of the materials which is important to know before any end application. The Figure 5 is showing a tensile testing report of three samples A₁ (100:2.5:5:5 (polyester resin: Hardener: Bamboo fiber: Banana fiber)), A₂ (100:2.5:7.5:2.5 (polyester resin: Hardener: Bamboo fiber: Banana fiber)) and A₃ (100:2.5:2.5:7.5 (polyester resin: Hardener: Bamboo fiber: Banana fiber)).

Figure 5. Tensile Strength Test result of sample A₁, A₂ and A₃
Source: Own Work

In this graph, three test results are plotted stress (%) in the y-axis and strain (%) in the x-axis. It can be seen that as stress increases, the strain also increases. The Maximum breaking strength of three samples are different. For Sample A₃, maximum strain is 4.06946, which is higher than the other two samples A₁ and A₂. Due to the higher percentage of banana fiber, the composite strength improves and indicates better strength. On the other hand, sample A₁ indicates maximum strain 3.4544 which is higher than A₁ (Maximum strain 3.45444). Overall, the presence of banana fiber in composite improves the tensile strength of composite.

Bending Strength Test

The bending test, often known as the bending strength test, evaluates the bending strength and other critical properties of materials (Glória, et al., 2017). Plastics, metals, ceramic materials, and fiber-reinforced plastics (FRP) are all subjected to destructive materials testing. Tests for bending have a similar order. ASTM D790 is used to evaluate the flexural strength of plastics and composite materials. Flexural strength is the capacity of a material to resist breaking or cracking under bending stress (De Bilbao, et al., 2008). When creating a product that has to withstand pressure or bear loads, it is crucial to

know which material or materials will function the best. ASTM D790 is widely used in the evaluation of electrical insulating materials, thermoplastics and thermosets, reinforced and unreinforced plastics, and high modulus

composites (Zhu, Peled, & Mobasher, 2011). Among the different method, Customers can use Bluehill Universal's Expression Builder to enter the test speed with optimization (Glória, et al., 2017).

Figure 6. Bending Test result of Sample A₁, A₂ and A₃

Source: Own Work

The Figure 6 expresses the bending test results of three composite samples A1, A2 and A3. The plot shows stress (%) on the y-axis and strain (%) on the x-axis. Due to presence of bamboo fiber, sample A2 shows good bending strain result (maximum strain 3.13396). Beside that, sample A1 contains equal volume of bamboo and banana fibers which ensure the second highest bending strength scores strain 3.13396. Hence, the lowest bamboo fibers present in the sample A3, which shows lowest bending strain (2.01356) in result. Moreover, enrichment of bamboo fiber in composite ensures the highest bending properties.

Impact Test

The purpose of an impact test is to see the mechanics a material will display when subjected to stress loading that results in the specimen deforming, fracturing, or rupturing right away (Navaranjan, & Neitzert, 2017). The Charpy impact test, sometimes referred to as the Charpy V-notch test, is a high strain-rate test in which a controlled weight pendulum swung

from a predetermined height is struck against a standard notched specimen (Durieux, et al., 2024). The impact test is a useful tool for determining how much energy the specimen absorbs during fracture. The typical Charpy-V notch specimen is 10 mm square, 55 mm long, and machined on one face to have a tip radius of 0.25 mm and a notch that is 2 mm deep. Sub-size Charpy specimens having a thickness of less than 10 mm may occasionally be evaluated (Yamini, et al., 2023).

The Charpy specimen's center line is notched in accordance with standards using a unique broach to produce the necessary V-Notch with the right measurements and surface quality (Nossa, et al., 2019). 2.5 mm x 10 mm, 5 mm x 10 mm, or 7.5 mm x 10 mm can be used to create sub-size specimens (Sutherland, 2018). There are special considerations for pipelines and threaded fasteners (Nascimento, et al., 2018) Either room temperature or a predetermined temperature, such as -20°C, -10°C, 0°C, +10°C, or +20°C, is used to test specimens. The specimen is struck on the face opposite the notch by the pendulum

after being supported at both ends by an anvil (Durieux, et al., 2024). The Figure 7 shows that sample A2 has the highest impact test results, with bamboo demonstrating greater force compared to fiber. Increased bamboo fiber in

composites increases impact strength due to good interfacial bonding, while samples A2 and A3 have poor interfacial adhesion and delimitation, as the composite's thickness is not reinforced by fibers.

Figure 7. Impact Test Result of Sample A₁, A₂ and A₃

Source: Own Work

Thermal Conductivity Test

The rate at which heat is transported by conduction through a unit cross-section area of a material when there is a temperature gradient perpendicular to the area is known as thermal conductivity (Folorunso, et al., 2019). The attribute of a material that reflects its capacity to transport heat is called thermal conductivity (k). Only in the presence of a temperature gradient in a solid (or stationary fluid) medium can conduction take place (Van den Berg, et al., 2023). Heat moves in a conductor's direction when the temperature drops. Thus higher molecular energy is correlated with higher temperature (Folorunso, et al., 2019). This transfer will go on until the temperature reaches thermal equilibrium. The size of the temperature differential and the particular thermal properties

of the material determine how quickly heat is transported (Yamini, et al., 2023). A thick metal plate with the same diameter as C makes up the lower portion of the steam chamber, or B. The upper section consists of a hollow chamber with two side tubes for steam inflow and outflow. T1 and T2 thermometers are placed into two of C's and B's holes, respectively (Filik, et al., 2021).

Thermal conductivity is quantified in the units of W/mK. From the Figure 8, It can be said $A2 > A1 > A3$. That means the thermal conductivity increase when the ratio of bamboo fiber increase. The banana fiber is not so good in terms of thermal conductivity, which is why sample A3 has lower conductivity than samples A1&A2. So, bamboo fiber is good conductor than banana fiber.

Figure 8. Thermal Conductivity Test of Sample A₁, A₂ and A₃
 Source: Own Work

Thermal Resistance Test

The ratio of a material's temperature differential between its two faces to its heat flow rate per unit area, expressed as $Kffm^2/W$, is known as thermal resistance (Yamini, et al., 2023). Before using consistent state strategies for computation, the experimental setting needs to reach a condition of harmony. On the other hand, since temporal approaches rely on temperature versus time curves plotted during warming, harmony is not necessary for calculations to be performed

(Nascimento, et al., 2018). Two metal plates (often brass), a steam chamber, the test to be assessed, and two thermometers to detect the temperature slope make up the most basic experimental setup for Lee's Plate method (Asmare, & Jamir, 2023). While convection is being discussed, the entire arrangement is stopped in order to remove any remaining conduction effects, even if it might be a significant issue in calculations (Shinde, et al., 2018).

Figure 9. Thermal Resistance of sample A₁, A₂ and A₃
 Source: Own Work

The bottom metal circle loses heat energy to convection, and the poor conductor exchanges heated energy with it. As a result, after a set amount of time, each metal plate will achieve a constant temperature (Asmare, & Jamir, 2023). The warm conductivity can be measured by comparing the two distinct temperatures. In a harmonic environment, the overall heat flux from the weak conductor to the foot plate determines the heat conventionally lost by that circle (Navaranjan, & Neitzert, 2017). Thermal resistance is a property of heat and a measurement of the difference in temperature at which a substance or object resists the flow of heat. Because sample A3 has 100:2.5:2.5:7.5 (polyester resin: hardener: bamboo fiber: banana fiber), it has the maximum level of thermal resistance, as seen in the graph. Therefore, the thermal conductivity and thermal resistance of the insulation material can be measured at room temperature and at normal pressure in the steady state. The Figure 9 demonstrates that sample A3, which has a higher proportion of banana fiber, has better thermal resistance than samples A1 and A2, which have a similar or higher bamboo: banana ratio. As a result, the composite's thermal resistance and thermal conductivity increase as the percentage of bamboo and banana, respectively.

Conclusion

In summary, it can be said that changes in the percentage of fiber do not affect the hybrid composite made of bamboo and banana. The results of the tensile strength test show that sample A2 (100:2.5:7.5:2.5) is the strongest, whereas sample A3 (100:2.5:2.5:7.5) (polyester resin: Hardener: Bamboo fiber: Banana fiber) has the highest tensile strength. Specimen A2 may absorb a greater force in an impact test before undergoing deformation. There is an extreme contrast between thermal conductivity and thermal resistance. When more bamboo fiber is added to these hybrid composites, the quantity of thermal resistance reduces and the thermal conductivity increases. Conversely, adding more banana fiber to a composite results in a decrease

in heat conductivity and an increase in thermal resistance. Ultimately, it is evident that a 75:25 fiber ratio can seem better than an equal ratio. For increased tensile strength and heat resistance, use "Sample A3" 100:2.5:2.5:7.5 (polyester resin: Hardener: Bamboo fiber: Banana fiber); for increased strength, force absorption, and thermal conductivity, use "Sample A2" 100:2.5:7.5:2.5 (polyester resin: Hardener: Bamboo fiber: Banana fiber). Both sample A2 and sample A3 can develop into more sophisticated composite materials by carrying out the extra research. These composites could be used for furniture, door covers, false ceilings, cars, firefighting equipment, and more based on their demonstrated qualities.

Author Contributions

All authors of this research article contributed in every process, from sample making to sample testing, plotting data and writing the article. Authors are deeply grateful to the Dhaka University of Engineering and Technology (DUET) for the support regarding mechanical and thermal test.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no potential conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

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